

Optimization of the Liquid Diffusion Process to produce Nb₃Sn Films for Superconducting Radio Frequency Applications

M. Zanierato^{1,3}, O. Azzolini¹, R. Caforio^{1,3}, V. Garcia^{1,2}, E. Chyhyrynets^{1,3}, G. Keppel¹, F. Stivanello¹, C. Pira¹

¹ INFN, Laboratori Nazionali di Legnaro, Legnaro (Padova), Italy.

² Università di Ferrara, Ferrara, Italy.

³ Università di Padova, Padova, Italy.

INTRODUCTION

The performance of the Nb bulk cavities has now reached the theoretical limits imposed by the material. It is necessary to look at other superconducting materials, among which the most promising is Nb₃Sn.

This material has a critical temperature of 18 K, twice the one of Nb. The high critical temperature significantly reduces the surface resistance, allowing to obtain cavities with accelerating performances at 4,2 K comparable to those of Nb bulk at 2 K. This allows the reduction of cryogenic costs, since it is not necessary to pump the helium bath to obtain high performances. A second advantage of the Nb₃Sn is that the theoretical limit of the maximum accelerating gradient is increased in elliptical cavities from 50 MV/m (Nb) to theoretical 100 MV/m (Nb₃Sn). Another important aspect of Nb₃Sn is a high value of critical field of 24 T. This feature makes the material suitable for all applications where a high magnetic field is required, such as cavities for finding dark matter particles as Axions.

The critical aspect of Nb₃Sn on Nb bulk (Nb₃Sn/Nb) cavities is the thermal quench due to the inhomogeneity and insufficient thin film thickness less of 1 μm obtainable via Vapour Tin Diffusion (VTD) [1]. Along the years different coating methods for Nb₃Sn have been developed, in particular Liquid Tin Diffusion (LTD) has been deeply studied at LNL from 2005 to 2009 [2, 3]. LTD presents no thickness limitation, 5 microns Nb₃Sn film thickness is easily achieved, but RF test on 6 GHz cavities showed poor SRF performances. The limitations have been related to the presence of unreacted Sn on the cavity cell bottom part.

The renewed interest on Nb₃Sn pushed our group to upgrade the original LTD protocol, studying in particular the nucleation steps, in order to remove the Sn excess problem. In this paper a new LTD process and first results achieved are presented.

EXPERIMENTAL PART

The system consists of a pumping system, a linear manipulator, a furnace used for heating the crucible containing the tin, a furnace used for annealing samples, and a water jacket. The main chamber is made of Inconel. The 6 GHz prototype cavities are made by spinning. Niobium substrates are subjected to ultrasonic bath and subsequent BCP (Buffer Chemical Polishing) HF: HNO₃: H₃PO₄ in a 1:1:2 ratio from five to ten minutes. The

substrates prepared for pre-nucleation are subsequently anodized at 20 V for one minute in NaOH solution to form a 70 nm Nb₂O₃ layer. Finally, for the cavities, high pressure rinsing is carried out in distilled water (120 bar 5 minutes); for the samples the rinsing is carried out in ultrasound.

The samples are fixed to the manipulator by niobium wires. The system is heated and evacuated to a base pressure of 10⁻⁸ mbar. The hybrid process with nucleation is divided into various steps as described in Fig. 1.

Ramping: the lower furnace is switched on immediately to obtain degassing of the crucible in the bottom of the chamber, an hour later the upper furnace is switched on.

Pre-Nucleation: The substrates are located at the centre of the chamber in the annealing zone and remain there for 3 to 9 h at 600°C.

Coating: the upper furnace increases the temperature of the system to 1000°C and remains stable from 2 to 9 h.

Dipping: The substrates are immersed in the crucible at 1000°C from 0.5 to 7 h by means of the manipulator.

Steam annealing: the samples brought back to the centre of the chamber are heated from 7.5 to 77 h in the presence of the tin vapours of the crucible at 1000°C.

Annealing: the lower furnace decreases in temperature blocking the tin landing on the surface of the samples allowing annealing from 15 to 84 h. The temperature of upper furnace should be near 1000°C.

Cooling: the samples are brought to the upper area of the water jacket to fix the phase.

Fig. 1 Temperature profiles of furnaces in the hybrid process with nucleation step for 6 GHz cavities.

The new process has been developed using small Nb bulk samples (30x15x3 mm). For each run 2 samples at time have been used: one anodized as in the VTD [1] and one just polished with BCP as in the old process to evaluate possible influence in the film growth. Once the optimal process has been defined 2 different 6 GHz elliptical cavities have been coated: the first one has been sectioned for morphological characterization and the second one has been measured in a RF test at 4.2 K.

The old processes involved a heating ramp, dipping step and annealing in the presence and absence of steam. The limits found in this process are the formation of percolating paths inside the material with consequent incorporation of tin on the surface and little sintering of the grains. In the new processes the samples are anodized to favour nucleation at 600 ° C, the coating step allows a growth of the Nb₃Sn crystallites before the dipping step. The annealing sequence is used to first have a slow evaporation of the Sn while maintaining a correct stoichiometry, then to eliminate the residual tin on the surface and favour sintering.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Film growth on Nb substrates present percolation paths on the surface as in previous processes [5]. Anodization limit the phenomenon by allowing densification along the entire film [4]. Controlled nucleation in the nucleation and coating steps before the dipping process allows the growth of a stoichiometric film without metal tin on the surface regardless of the geometric complexity of the substrate as shown in Fig. 2. Controlled nucleation results in a tin concentration of 23-37% versus 26-65% without the pre-nucleation step.

Fig. 2 (Left) SEM micrograph of the sample without anodization, Sn residual tin is present. (Right) Image of the inner surface of the anodized cavity, only grains of Nb₃Sn are present.

A film thickness of about 5 microns has been chosen for the cavities with dipping times of half an hour to avoid the possible formation of cracks.

The cavities coated with the new process show absence of unreacted Tin in all the internal surface, contrary to the process in which a large amount Sn drops were present on the surface (see Fig. 3). However EDS characterizations reveal a surface contamination of chromium (from 5% to 20%), iron and nickel are extremely localized on the external surface of the cavity. The source of contamination is probably the vapour tension of the Inconel chamber during the annealing step. The internal surface instead has high sintering and no EDS contaminants are evident, the

stoichiometry obtained is Nb 65% Sn 35% with possible residual tin at the grain boundary. At the XRD is visible only the Nb₃Sn phase.

Fig. 3 (A) Cavity synthesized with hybrid methodology external and internal surfaces (B, C) [3]. (D) Cavity with controlled nucleation external and internal surfaces (E).

A RF test has been done in cavity 2. The cavity presents quality factors $Q_0 = 4 \cdot 10^5$ as shown in Fig. 4 (comparable with the old process), with a Tc of 11.5K.

We have identified two main causes of this low performances: film poisoning by Cr and Fe; a problem with the furnace that limited temperature during the annealing step producing a Sn enrichment at the grain boundary. Possible solutions are the insertion of a Nb screen between samples and Inconel chamber and a longer annealing time to compensate furnace limitations.

Fig. 1 Q vs. accelerating field measured at 4.2 K for Nb₃Sn 6GHz cavity.

CONCLUSION

A new LTD process has been developed and optimized with the introduction of controlled nucleation via substrate anodization. The new process avoids the presence of unreacted Sn, providing a single Nb₃Sn phase with a good stoichiometry and morphology. Surface resistance however remains higher than Nb at 4.2 K in the first cavity coated. In the future months, the possible causes of contamination and temperature limitation will be addressed and the role of each process step in film performances and morphology will be deeply studied.

- [1] S. Posen et al., Superconductor Science and Technology, 2017.
- [2] A. Rossi et al., Proc. SRF (Berlin), 2009.
- [3] S. Deambrosis et al., SRF. 2007. p. 393-399.
- [4] M. Zanierato, Master thesis, University of Padua, Italy, 2020.
- [5] N. Pretto, Master thesis, University of Padua, Italy, 2006.